

Impact Factor : 4.532
Karnataka Reg. No. : 48/159/CE/0103/2013

Print ISSN: 2321-3604
Online ISSN: 2321-3612

ANNAI VAILANKANNI ARTS & SCIENCE COLLEGE

(Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Thiruchirappalli)

Thanjavur - 613 007, Tamil Nadu, India.

Special Issue

January 2017

Everyone thinks of changing the world,
But no one thinks of changing **HIMSELF...**

:- Leo Tolstoy

In Associate with
**Primax International Journal of Commerce
and Management Research**

(Primax Commerce and Management Research Academy, Bangalore-56, Karnataka)

Contents

Sl.No.	Title of the Articles	Page No.
1	An Empirical Study - Dimensions of Employee Engagement to Influence The Company's Productivity In Selected Boiler Companies in Trichy - B. Deepa & Dr. M. Sheik Mohamed	1 - 5
2	A Study on The Impact The Sales Promotional Activities of Cosmetic Users In Virudhunagar District, Tamilnadu - C. Shyamala Alais Porkodi & Dr. S. Shahul Hameed	6 - 9
3	A Study on Cropping Pattern in Thanjavur District - Dr. A. Kanmani Joan of Arc & S. D. Kowsalya	10 - 15
4	A Study on Perception of LIC Policy Holders in Thanjavur District - Dr. Kanmani Joan of Arc & P. Muthamil Thirumagal	16 - 21
5	The Demographic Characteristics of The Customer Engagement and their Effects at Unisex Saloon in Tiruchirappalli City. - Dr. G. Rabia Jahani Farzana & R. Banu Priya	22 - 28
6	Job Burnout and Psychological Capital - Dr. G. Rabia Jahani Farzana & G. A.Vaakshi	29 - 32
7	The Impact of online Banking and Insurances in Life Scenario - Dr. G. Rabia Jahani Farzana, N. Sathyapriya & K. Meenalochani	33 - 38
8	A Study on The Impact of Lean Practices on Innovation in Small Medium Kitchenware Industries - Dr. G. S. Subashini & Dr. V. Sumathy	39 - 43
9	Self Help Group Women also Having Stress - Dr. L. Balamurugan & Dr. V. Sumathy	44 - 50
10	Rural and Urban Clients Perception towards Micro Credit Services of Gramavidyal Microfinance Limited In Trichy Division - Dr. N. Shaik Mohamed & A. Mehathab Sheriff	51 - 56
11	Employees' Perspective on Human Resource Management Practices in Cement Industries - Hajee Dr. R. Khader Mohideen & A. Sophia Alphonse	57 - 63
12	A Study on Post Office Savings in Rural Areas with Reference to Tiruchirappalli District - Dr. S. Gulam Mohamed & M. Shajahan	64 - 69
13	A Study on the awareness level of Mutual Fund Investors in Mutual Funds with reference to Thanjavur District - Dr. S. Suresh & Dr. R. Kannappa	70 - 76
14	An Overview of Financial Performance of TDCC Bank Ltd - Dr. V. Jaisankar & A. Ansar Ali	77 - 82

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF LEAN PRACTICES ON INNOVATION IN SMALL MEDIUM KITCHENWARE INDUSTRIES

Dr.V.Sumathy²Dr.G.S.Subashini¹

Abstract

The Functional Innovation is an integrated approach to creative ideation and problem solving which incorporates aspects from several well. Improving innovation and adding value to the customers and organizations is essential in today's economy. Lean manufacturing is a systematic method for the elimination of waste within a manufacturing system. Leaning out the process refers to the reduction of non-value added steps related to creating a product or service. Toyota's lean approach to manufacturing focuses on seven wastes to improve overall customer value. Organizations that learn how to use lean thinking and innovation as compatible tools will accelerate past the competition. The aim of this paper is to discuss the impact of lean practices on innovation. A structured questionnaire survey from the production managers in kitchenware industries. Respondents opinion towards the lean production Principles based on organization climate dimension innovation were analyzed.

Key words: Innovation, Lean practices, organization climate

Introduction

Lean production is still prevalent today and practiced by many organizations globally. With greater global exposure and responsibility to customers worldwide, many organizations are asking if leaning out production processes is enough to compete. More customers desire rapidly released innovative products and services. Organizations are compelled to respond and integrate current lean practices with innovation to exceed customer expectations. This critical paradigm shift is one of the greatest challenges facing production and service driven companies today. According to a 2015 Boston Consulting Group innovation survey, 79 percent of respondents ranked innovation as a top-three priority at their company. Another outcome from the same survey suggested that respondents seek to speed up their processes and embrace new technologies. They see well-run, lean processes as essential to this transformation. These results mean organizations and their leadership have a vested interest in creating methods to intersect lean and innovation practices.

Lean Thinking and Innovation

Organizations having at least two core functions, hopefully operating at the same time. The first function accomplishes whatever we do as a business. Whether it is selling shoes, making kitchen wares, or lending money, the first function implements the day-to-day business. The second function is the improvement part of the business. It is where we come up with new businesses, products, services, and improvements to our existing business. We use lean thinking for the first function and innovation for the second function.

Innovations are used to create new businesses, products or services. But, it is also used to improve a process. Innovation takes us from the current state to a future state. The lean thinking tool comes in to play when we want to execute the innovation. An organizational lean design alone can't deliver the promise of innovation. If both lean and innovation frameworks are integrated successfully the positive result might be disruptive and a competitive advantage. This is the challenge for many senior leaders as they recognize the importance of not only a lean manufacturing or corporate environment, but the need to continually innovate to exceed their customer's expectations.

Supporters believe that Lean can contribute to more innovation, by freeing up resources that can be rather used advantageously to innovation (Johnstone et al., 2011; Reinertsen & Shaeffer, 2005). On the other hand, opponents believe that by being "too Lean" companies may weaken their long-term innovative ability by being too concerned with removing non-value added activities, considered waste (Chen & Taylor, 2009; Lewis, 2000; Lindeke et al., 2009).

Organizational innovation is supposed to trigger positive changes in efficiency, competitiveness and quality (Sledzik, 2013).

Lean Production system use a variety of techniques and tools for eliminating waste like: Just-in-time, cellular manufacturing, Value Stream Mapping, 5s, Kanban (Pull) systems, Kaizen, synchronous manufacturing, Poka-Yoke (Manea, 2013). These are innovations, resulting from a scarcity of resources and intense domestic

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, Kumbhavarai Nachiyar Government Arts College For Women(Autonomous), Thanjavur

² Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, M.R. Government Arts College, Mannargudi

competition in the Japanese automobile industry in 1980's. Lean Innovation System is another approach, which can balance innovation and Lean within the firm. The point is to interpret and incorporate Lean principles into innovation development processes. "It applies the Lean concepts to the R&D facilities to generate product differentiation with reduced resources and waste" (Chen & Taylor, 2009). This shows how Lean thinking focused on customer value can be helpful in improving the structure and efficiency of innovative R&D activities.

Organization Climate (OC) concerned with the perception and feelings which each individual matures of the organization environment as it is actually generated by the culture development process. Since organizational climate consists of more empirically accessible elements such as behavioral and attitudinal characteristics, the researcher has taken OC for the study. Organizational climate is more behaviorally oriented in that climates for creativity, innovation, safety, or service, for example, may be found in the workplace. These climates represent employees' perceptions of organizational policies, practices, and procedures, and subsequent patterns of interactions and behaviors that support creativity, innovation, safety, or service in the organization. Thus climate can be understood as a surface manifestation of culture (Schein, 1985; Schneider, 1990). The dimension which was taken for the study was mentioned below:

- **Reward System**
It denotes the degree to which people are recognized and rewarded for good work, rather than being ignored, criticized or punished when something goes wrong.
- **Organization clarity**
It refers to the feeling that things are well organized and that goals and responsibility are clearly defined, rather than being disorderly confused or chaotic.
- **Standards of performance**
The emphasis of standards of performance placed on quality performance and achievement of results, including the degree to which meaningful and challenging goals are set at every level of the organization.
- **Warmth and support**
The feeling that friendliness is a valued norm and that people trust, respect and support one another. It denotes the feeling that good relationships prevail in the day-to-day work of organization.
- **Leadership**
It refers to the extent to which people take leadership roles as the need arises and are rewarded for successful leadership

- **Communication**
Here, communication denotes the degree to which important information is shared up, down and sideways.
- **Innovation**
Innovation refers to the extent to which new ideas are sought and used in all areas of the organization.
- **Feedback and Controls**
The extent the organization uses the reporting, comparing and correcting procedures such as evaluation and financial audit.
- **Teamwork**
It refers to the amount of understanding, cooperation and support demonstrated between different levels and groups in organization.
- **Involvement**
It denotes the extent to which responsibility for decision making is broadly shared in the organization.

Research Design and Methodology

This research was performed in kitchenware industries in Chennai at Tamil Nadu. Seventy nine industries were selected as sample on the basis of stratified random sampling. Organizational climate questionnaire that measures the innovation dimension was used for this study. the primary data was collected through questionnaire which consists 5- point likerts scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Cronbach alpha reliability test was applied and the result was found to be relatively high(0.73).hence, it was found that the questionnaire used for assessing the adoption of lean production principles based on organization climate was found to be reliable. The main goal of this research is to describe the data and characteristics about what is being studied. So, the researcher uses the descriptive research design to study the implementation intensity of lean practices and organizational climate in kitchenware industries. To find out the significant relationship between organizational climate and degree of adoption of lean principles independent t-test was performed.

Objectives

- To group the industries based on organization climate.
- To analyze the significant relationship between DDC of Lean Production Principles based on Organizational Climate

Based on the objectives lay down for the study, the following hypotheses were formulated to test the selected variables. There is no significant relationship between and degree of adoption of lean principles.

Organization Climate

Table - 1 : Distribution of Industries based on the Organization Climate Dimensions

Dimensions	Strongly disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly agree	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Reward System	0	0	8	10.1	16	20.3	37	46.8	18	22.8
Organization Clarity	0	0	0	0.0	35	44.3	24	30.4	20	25.3
Standards of Performance	0	0	6	7.6	3	3.8	52	65.8	18	22.8
Warmth and support	0	0	9	11.4	5	6.3	48	60.8	17	21.5
Leadership	3	3.8	16	20.3	9	11.4	35	44.3	16	20.3
Communication	0	0.0	0	0.0	13	16.5	37	46.8	29	36.7
Innovation	3	3.8	8	10.1	3	3.8	42	53.2	23	29.1
Feedbacks and Controls	0	0	0	0.0	21	26.6	42	53.2	16	20.3
Team Work	0	0	3	3.8	7	8.9	43	54.4	26	32.9
Involvement	0	0	6	7.6	25	31.6	28	35.4	20	25.3

Source : Primary Data; % - denotes percentage; count-denotes frequency

Organization Climate (OC) concerned with the perception and feelings which each individual matures of the organization environment. Distribution of industries according to organization climate dimensions and the type of organization based on OC dimensions has done.

Table 1 illustrates that 88.6 percent of industries agreed that the performance standards are high in the kitchenware industries. According to Lean and Lanner once such control has been established, a lean business must relentlessly strive for improvement and perfection.

Further it reveals that 87.3 percent of industries agreed that industries were practicing teamwork. The results were supported by Farhana Ferdousi et al. (2009); the authors' findings revealed that 56% of the companies had team based structures and the remaining companies had functional structures. The author had insisted that team work is one of the core concepts of lean production. Regarding communication, the percent of industries agreed were found to be 83.5 and it is found that 64.6 percentages of industries were agreed with leadership. It is exposed that information was accurate and leadership is provided, accepted and rewarded based on expertise. Further the result was also supported by Abend (2000) and Reichard (2007); where the authors noted that effective leaders must make the capital investment decisions that enable the organization to respond to market demands. 82.3 percent of industries agreed with warmth and support. It was found that Warmth and support are characteristic of the organization.

As far as innovation is concerned, 82.3 percentages of industries agreed. Results show that the organization is innovative and open to new ideas. Lean and Innovation do not represent such a significant contrasting problem in practice as believed by some of the theorist and assumption. this is because the majority of surveyed industries have innovation high on their agenda they managed to succeed with innovation and lean by adapting lean to research and development department and not the opposite.

73.5 percentage of industries agreed that industries practice feedback and control. This reveals that Controls are used to provide guidance and solve problems. The finding coincides with Richard G. Ligus(2006) ; the author suggested that, if all of the motivational factors can be integrated as part of the initiative, then the organization can be moved forward with much less resistance, creating an enhanced opportunity for success. In addition to that the author quoted that lean organization should focus on sustaining change through leadership, empowerment, and

communication. The dominant principle of organization has shifted, from management in order to control an enterprise to leadership in order to bring out the best in people and to respond quickly to change. On the issue of reward it shows that 69.6 percent of industries agreed that industries' efforts and performance are recognized and rewarded positively in kitchenware industries. Findings were supported by Little and McKinna (2005); where the authors stated that recognition and rewards from top management will serve as a booster for participation and continuous improvement.

Involvement of employees in kitchenware industries was found to be 60.7 percent. This shows that participation in decision making is high in these industries. Pil and MacDuffie, (1995); MacDuffie, (1996); Cua et al., (2001); Shan and Ward, (2003) supported that employee involvement accounts for the role of employees in achieving the goals and objectives of the above programs. Developing cross-functional teams, empowering employees and decentralizing decision-making are ways through which firms accomplish the goals of lean management. 55.7 percent of industries agreed that industries have clarity in the goals and responsibility. Organization is well organized with clearly defined goals and responsibility.

So it is concluded that 88.6 percent of industries agreed that the performance standards are high in the kitchenware industries. 20.3 percent of industries were found to disagree with leadership. Researcher Michael H. McGivern has argued that the four thrusts of lean manufacturing are leadership, team based culture, communication systems, simultaneous development and continuous improvement process. So, the findings reveal that few kitchenware industries have to improve their leadership quality for better business performance.

Organization Types based on Organizational Climate Dimensions

Table - 2 : Organization Type according to Organizational Climate Dimensions

Organizational climate	Frequency	Percent
Improvised	9	11.4
Supportive	34	43.0
Enlightened	36	45.6

Source : Primary Data

The scores for organizational climate dimensions were computed by the scores developed by George Manning et al. (1996). The author mentioned four types of organization based on their scores. High scores (i.e) mean value 4.1 to 5 represents enlightened and mean value 3.1 to 4 represents supportive organization. Medium scores (i.e) mean value 2.1 to 3 represent improvised organizations. Further low scores (i.e) mean value 1 to 2 reflect exploitive organizations. It was interesting to find that after implementation of lean manufacturing, no organization was found to be exploitive. Since there was no exploitive organization, the researcher omitted that and took the remaining three types as shown in the table. The above table reveals that 45.6 percentage of industries were found to be enlightened and 43 percentage of industries were supportive. 11.4 percentage of industries were found to be improvised.

DOA of Lean Production Principles and Organization Climate

Table - 3 : Respondents Opinion towards DOA of Lean Production, Principles based on Organization Climate

Lean production principles	Organizational climate	Mean	SD	T	P-value	Multiple comparison test
DOA	Improvised	2.43	0.61	12.569	0.00*	Enlighten > Supportive, Improvised
	Supportive	2.86	0.53			
	Enlightened	3.50	0.81			

Source : Primary Data; * - 1 percent level of significance

The results reveal that there is a significant difference between the organizational climate and DOA in kitchenware industries. Table 3 provides the actual results from the independent t-test and Levine's Test for Equality of Variances. In addition to that, it was observed from the table that the t-value was found to be 12.569 and p- value was 0.00.

Since the p-value was significant at 1 percent level of significance results show that there is a significant difference between the organizational climate and DOA of lean practices.

Degree of adoption of lean production principles was found to be high in enlightened organization with the mean 3.50 when compared to Supportive and Improvised with the mean 2.86 and 2.43. It was revealed from the table that lean production practices were found to be adopted more in the enlightened organization since the enlightened organizations are reputed well with leadership, teamwork, communication; innovation degree of adoption was high. The results were supported by Richard G. Ligus et al. (2006) who suggested that if all of the motivational factors can be integrated as part of the initiative, then the organization can be moved forward with much less resistance, creating an enhanced opportunity for success. In addition to that the author quoted that lean organization should focus on sustaining change through leadership, empowerment, and communication.

Since the p-value was 0.00, further post-hoc multiple comparison test was performed and results show that the enlightened organization was found to be superior to Supportive and Improvised organization.

Conclusion

Lean thinking helps us make innovations real. It was interesting to find that after implementation of lean manufacturing, no organization was found to be exploitive. There is a significant difference between the organizational climate and DOA in kitchenware industries. It was revealed that lean production practices were found to be adopted more in the enlightened organization since the enlightened organizations are reputed well with leadership, teamwork, communication and innovation. The degree of adoption was found to be high. At its core, lean thinking is about humanity. As you learn more about lean and how it ties to respecting people, you can see how lean thinking should always get along with innovation.

References

- Chen, H., & Taylor, R. (2009, August). Exploring the impact of Lean management on innovation capability. In *Management of Engineering & Technology, 2009 PICMET 2009*. Portland International Conference on (pp. 826-834) IEEE

- Farhana Ferdousi (2009), "An Investigation of Manufacturing Performance Improvement through Lean Production: A Study on Bangladeshi Garment Firms", *International journal of business and management*, vol.4, No 9, September 2009.
- George L. Hodge, Kelly Goforth Ross, Jeff A. Joines & Kristin Thoney (2011), *Adapting lean manufacturing principles to the textile industry*, *Production Planning & Control: The Management of Operations*, April 2011, 22:3, 237-247 Taylor & Francis DOI: 10.1080/09537287.2010.498577.
- Johnstone, C., Piraudeau, G., & Pettersson, J. A. (2011). Creativity, innovation and Lean sigma: a controversial combination?. *Drug discovery today*, 16(1), 50-57.
- Lewis, M. A. (2000). Lean production and sustainable competitive advantage. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 20(8), 959-978.
- Lindeke, R. R., Wyrick, D. A., & Chen, H. (2009). Creating change and driving innovation in highly automated and Lean organizations: The Temporal Think Tank™ (T3™). *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 25(6), 879-887
- Manea, D. (2013). Lean Production—Concept And Benefits. *Review of General Management*, (1), 164-171.
- Schneider, B. (2000), "The psychological life of organizations". In N. M. Ashkanasy, C. P. M. Wilderon, & M. F. Peterson (Eds.), *Handbook of organizational culture and climate* (pp. xvii-xxi). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Sledzik K., (2013), Schumpeter's view on innovation and entrepreneurship (in:) *Management Trends in Theory and Practice*, (ed.) Stefan Hittmar, Faculty of Management Science and In-formatics, University of Zilina & Institute of Management by University of Zilina
- Womack, J.P., & Jones, D.T. (2010) *Lean Thinking: banish waste and create wealth in your corporation*, simon and schuster.